

MoveD – ORD Guidelines for Swiss Movement Laboratories

Section 4: Data Analysis

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1. Metadata

The following metadata should be captured during statistical data analysis. For imaging data and EEG, the interpretation of graphs and images may be more suitable. Statistical analysis may therefore not have been performed, and the metadata content should be adjusted accordingly. For ultrasound, use cases which may help in interpretation can be found at <https://www.ultrasoundcases.info/cases/musculo-skeletal-joints-and-tendons/>.

Table 1: Metadata collected during data analysis

Title	Content/Format	Comment
Date of data analysis	[YYYY-MM-DD]	According to International Organization for Standardization 8601
Software(s) used for data analysis	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Name Manufacturer Version (software and used packages) Kind of data that were analyzed (kinematics, kinetics, EMG, accelerometer, IMU, EEG, plantar pressure, imaging, video) 	
Statistical analysis (if performed)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Statistical model Number of analyzed parameters Type of parameter (dependent, independent) 	Also report if only descriptive statistics were calculated

2. Source code, if applicable

The following section is only applicable if the statistical software used produces code.

2.1 Minimal requirement:

- Codes are saved with version control
- A regular back-up of the code is performed
- Codes are reviewed (internally) before being used
- Code is organized in folders
- A readme file is included
- The readme file should contain the information needed to replicate the analysis (this includes the analysis environment; package versions)
- A clear link to the data location/repository should be provided, as well as a clear explanation of how to import the data

2.2 Ideal case:

- Code is uploaded to an openly accessible repository e.g. GitHub.
- At the very least, the commit for the version used in the analysis should be mentioned. Ideally, the used version is referenced as a release with a DOI/URI (using for example Zenodo to generate a DOI for the release).
- Code does not contain references to local folders so as to ensure interoperability
- All code is properly explained through inline comments so that others can use it without further instructions
- In the ideal case, code can be published in such a way that the data is directly downloaded from the repository and read when the code is run.

3 Description of source codes/readme file, if applicable

3.1 Minimal requirement:

- Project title
- Build status (development, testing, usage)
- Purpose of code/short description of project that the code was used for
- Code style e.g. R, Python or Matlab
- Date/time period when code was written
- Contributors to the code
- Copyright of the code/applicable licence --> <https://choosealicense.com/> for help
- Features of the code or the different parts of the code
- How the code should be used

3.2 Ideal case:

- Detailed high-level documentation: Description of different code components and how they are linked. The aim is to get an overview of the code and know where to start looking if a specific problem is encountered.

4 References

International Organization for Standardization. (2024). *Date and time format*.
<https://www.iso.org/iso-8601-date-and-time-format.html>